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BONNY RESIDENTS' PERCEPTION OF NLNG CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY PROGRAMS: A STUDY OF IBANI HOUR ON WAZOBIA 94.1FM

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Abstract: This study investigated the perception of residents of Bonny about the Corporate Social Responsibility programmes of the NLNG Company as portrayed by 'Ibani' Hour" on Wazobia FM, Port Harcourt. The theoretical framework adopted in the study was the corporate social responsibility theory and perception theory. The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey design. The population or the universe of the study comprised the total number of subjects in a research. The population of the study according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria

Official Gazette, the National Population Commission (2006) was projected from 214,983 to

254,820 growth rate of 18 years. The sample size for the study was 384 residents drawn from the Meyer's (1979) sampling table and multi-stage cluster sampling were used by the researcher. This study made use of the questionnaire and personal interviews. The data were presented using tables and percentages and analysed with Likert Scale Mean Value using the Weighted Means Score (WMS). The findings revealed that all the respondents (379) representing 100% were aware

NLNG's "Ibani" Hour programme aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM. The majority of the respondents agreed to have been always exposed to NLNG's "Ibani" Hour programme on Wzobia FM on Mondays and Thursdays at 5 pm. The study established the programme's effectiveness as a communication and engagement tool. Based on the findings of the study, the study recommended that NLNG should leverage this platform "Ibani Hour" to further communicate its on-going and future CSR initiatives as consistent engagement and transparent communication will help maintain and potentially increase the positive perception of NLNG's CSR efforts among the residents of Bonny.

Keywords: Ibani Hour, Wazobia 94.1FM, Perception, NLNG, Corporate Social Responsibility, Bonny Residents

Introduction

Bonny Kingdom has been of great commercial significance since the arrival of the Portuguese on the Island in the 15th Century. Bonny is located in the Eastern part of the Nigeria Delta about 50km Southeast of Port Harcourt, the Rivers State Capital. The unique location of Bonny naturally made it a major trading port in the Southern Delta Area of Nigeria and a gateway to international trade for centuries past and presently. Thus, following the discovery of crude oil in commercial quantities in Oloibiri in 1956, the Shell Petroleum Development Company

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(SPDC), in 1956 established a crude oil export terminal in Bonny, a project that was facilitated by Bonny's natural deep harbour. This strategic natural endowment later influenced the established of other oil and gas multinational corporations including the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas, Ltd. NLNG, in Bonny. As would be expected, this mega project has contributed in no small measure to the economic and social development of Nigeria in general and Bonny Island in particular. According to Omotowa (2012), the company's Trains 1-6 of the project had gulped \$13 Billion since the inception of the company. Among other economic benefits, Train -7 would attract \$ 12 Billion (₦ 1.89 Trillion) in Foreign Direct Investment, FDI, into the Nigerian economy, generate additional \$3 Billion revenue for the Nigerian Government, and create additional 13,000 new jobs that would be of immense benefits to the host community – Bonny (Omotowa, 2012).

No doubt, with the huge resources at its disposal, the NLNG has contributed so much to the infrastructural and social development of Bonny. In 2019 for example, during the unveiling of the Bonny consulate Building, an NLNG Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) project Managing Director, Tony Attach noted that the project which was undertaken in synergy with Julius Berger, was in appreciation of the good relationship between the company and the Bonny Kingdom during the construction of Train 1-6 of the project. He then appealed for further support and understanding at the on-going Train -7 project.

The NLNG Ltd is a joint venture company whose shareholders are the Nigeria National Petroleum Company Ltd (NNPC) with a major shareholding of 49%. Other shareholders of the gas giant are the Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), with 25.6%, Total LNG Ltd, 15% and Eni International which holds 10.4% of the total shares. The NLNG is the world's biggest liquefied natural gas company. From its Bonny Island Liquefaction plant the company exports natural gas to Europe, Asia and the United States. Among other CSR programmes, the NLNG in collaboration with the Bonny community, sponsors the Bonny Vocational centre where youths are trained in vocational skills. Some of the training programmes for youths include skills training in welding and fabrication, electrical, electronics technicians programmes, ICT training, information technology (IT) training, website design, Microsoft word training, networking engineering, among others.

However, the most significant Corporate Social Responsibility project being undertaken by the NLNG is the on-going multi-billion Naira, 35.68km Bodo - Bonny Road project. According to Eguozie (2019) the road was envisaged by the Federal Government to be completed in 2022. The \$333 Million (101 .565 at the rate of \$1: 305) project runs through difficult swampy terrain and large water bodies traversing Ogoni, Andoni and Bonny territories (Eguzozie, 2019). The project which is still on-going has been described as the biggest Corporate Social Responsibility, (CSR) initiative by a private company in Nigeria. The road which has been on the drawing board for decades, when completed, would relieve Bonny citizens, residents are those doing business on the Island of centuries of the dangerous sea travels now made worse by incessant pirate attacks. The road would also open Bonny Island for further development. The King of Bonny, Edward Asimini William Dappa Pepple II. Edward I who eulogized the NLNG for initiating the project, described it as a major infrastructural development in Bonny.

Among other development projects, the coming of the NLNG may have triggered the citing of the Federal Polytechnic of Oil and Gas in Bonny. These laudable development projects bear testimony to the fact that the NLNG is a successful business organisation. The projects also indicate that social responsibility of multinational

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corporations has evolved over time to the extent that big business organisations are expected to integrate the economic, social and environmental imperatives in their activities. Thus, apart from the sponsorship of the Bonny Vocational Centre, the NLNG sponsors a radio programme 'Ibani' Hour on Wazobia 94.1 FM as an avenue to highlight its contributions to the development of Bonny and reach out to the wide world about the development strides embarked by the company in the area.

However, the company's activities in the area have their downsides including environmental pollution now suffered by the residents of Bonny on daily basis. Environmental pollution which affects the land, sea and entire atmosphere of Bonny community is an issue that cannot be glossed over. This is owing to the negative impact of environmental pollution on the wellbeing of the residents of Bonny. For instance, one of the effects of air pollution according to experts, is that long term exposure to environmental pollutants have been found to be associated with increased risk of cancer in elderly people (Muanya, 2016). Douglas (1998) noted that in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria communities hosting oil and gas corporations are confronted with environmental problems caused by the operations of the multinational oil and gas corporations, to the extent that the region has become one of the most polluted in the world. Experts have divided the environmental problems caused by the operations of oil and gas multinational into oil and nonoil related issues.

According to Mamudu et al. (2021), the non-oil related environmental problems include, coastal/river bank erosion, flooding, spread of exotic species, agricultural land degradation, depletion of aquatic life, inadequate sanitary and waste management. The oil related environmental problems to Douglas (1998) include oil spills gas flares, acid rain, flooding erosion and dredging of canals. Besides, equipment failure and sabotages have made oil spills to become endemic in the Niger Delta leading to pollution of farm lands and fish ponds, while gas flaring and emission of noxious gases into the atmosphere have become the order of the day (Douglas, 1998). Commenting on one of the most devastating oil spill incidents in the Niger Delta, Yishau (2012) noted that for many communities in the Niger Delta, oil spills are the beginning of wisdom. As a result, oil and gas companies are consistently named among the least trusted by the public. Mamudu et al., (2021) noted that the National Downstream Oil Regulatory Commission claimed that estimated 1.89 million barrels of petroleum were spilled into the Niger Delta in a space of 20 years, between

1976 and 1996. A natural consequence of this careless nature of oil explorations in the area, according to Oweifa (2004), is that the health of the people in this area is jeopardized to the extent that people often complain about health issues including breathing and skin lesions.

Ejikeme (2010) observes that the Oil Spill Intelligence Report, a 10 year study commissioned by Greenpeace, indicates that although Shell operates in more than 100 countries, 40 percent of its oil spills happen in Nigeria. This worrisome situation was corroborated by Baird (2010) who wrote that even as Nigeria has suffered most from oil drilling, oil accidents - large and small, which occur almost weekly, little was heard about the problem because the institution empowered to tell the story seems to have abdicated from its responsibilities. Sado (2016) agreed that Nigeria the dangers of environmental pollution arising from oil exploration and exploitation activities in the Niger delta have always been treated with levity. Besides, many inhabitants in the area have lost basic human rights, such as health, access to food, clean water and ability to work.

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Confirming this position, Akanbi (2013) while decrying the environmental degradation caused by the operations of oil and gas companies, observed that the quest for sustainability of the environment has put a question mark on banks that still lend to oil firms, whose operations involve, severe environmental and social risks. At a seminar for Business Editors and Financial Journalists, the point was made by Yakubu Shehu of the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation, (NDIC), that banks should shift attention from its traditional operations of deposit taking and credit advancement and focus on protection of the environment and the vulnerable in the country, like residents in Bonny — home to NLNG (Akanbi, 2013). Still on the dangers on the health of residents in communities hosting oil and gas cooperation's, Muanya (2016) indicates that long term exposure of human beings to polluted environment, according to Dr. Thuan Quoc Thach of the University of Hong-Kong, has an effect on mortality mainly from cardiopulmonary causes and lung cancer.

Conscious of these negative developments, the NLNG mounted a number of CSR programmes targeted at cushioning the adverse effects of their operations on residents of Bonny and to justify the humongous revenue generated from the company's activities located there. Notwithstanding, as a sign of some dissatisfaction with the operations of the NLNG, Bonny youths, in June 2021, protested over the non-implementation of the 2010 Local Content Act by the Company, among other demands. However, while responding to the protest, the company's manager in charge of corporate Affairs, Eneyo Fatai Williams described the NLNG as good corporate citizens that applies the principles of fairness and inclusiveness in engaging with its stakeholders and that all stakeholders in the community are trusted partners.

The Ibani Hour is a one-hour social orientation programme produced by the Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd, (NLNG) and aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM on Mondays and Thursdays between 5-6pm. The programme is conservational in nature. During the 'Ibani' Hour some CSR programmes of the NLNG in Bonny are highlighted. Beneficiaries of the company's skill acquisition programmes are made to speak about their experiences. According to some of them, the NLNG provides them with after training kits like laptops, desktops, electricity generating sets and cash awards to enable them start their businesses.

During Ibani Hour the need for residents of Bonny to maintain a clean environment through proper waste and sewage disposal systems is advocate. Besides, residents are enjoined during 'Ibani' flour to register in the health insurance scheme for which the NLNG guarantees 50 percent discount for every registered residents. The NLNG also subsidizes other health care issues for residents of Bonny. In some episodes of 'Ibani' dialect of the Ijaw language is taught by one of the presenters, while both marine and domestic safety tips are highlighted. The social contributions of the Youth Resource Centre, Bonny, to Youth residents in Bonny are also emphasized during 'Ibani' hour, among other social issues. The company seizes the opportunity of the programme to highlight the NLNG's corporate social responsibility programme to the audience. There is therefore the need to appraise the perception of Bonny residents of the programme in relation to the company's CSR.

Statement of the Problem

Despite its laudable corporate social responsibility, CSR programmes in Bonny, the NLNG, like other oil and gas corporations operating in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria, is also confronted with the challenge of achieving integrity and trust from its host community. In Bonny, it was this lack of trust that may have triggered the June 12, 2021 protest and others before it, by youths of Bonny. Apart from environmental pollution from oil

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spills, gas flaring is another unhealthy consequence of the operations of multinational oil and gas companies in the Niger Delta. According to Douglas (1998), gas flares have potentially harmful effects on the health and livelihood of nearby communities as they release poisonous chemicals like nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide and several volatile compounds like benzene, xylene as well as carcinogens like benzopyrene, toluene, xylene and hydrogen sulphide, into the atmosphere. The obvious consequences according to Argo (2001) are that humans like the residents of Bonny who are consistently exposed to such dangerous substances can suffer respiratory problems. Benzene, known to be emitted from gas flares is well recognized as a cause of leukemia and other blood related diseases (Akpan, 2003).

In fact, concern for the health of resident in communities hosting oil and gas multinational corporations, MNCs like Bonny and the quest for a sustainable environment even drew the ire of regulatory authorities in the financial sector, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and the Nigeria Deposit insurance (NDIC). The twin organization took interest in the health concerns of residents of the communities hosting oil and gas companies by questioning the rationale for continued credit extension by banks to organizations especially, those in the oil and gas sectors whose operations are not friendly to the environment. It was in support of the environmental health of the communities hosting oil and gas corporations that the Central Bank of Nigeria in 2011 introduced measures that were targeted at preventing banks from extending loans to organizations in the oil and gas sector whose operations are destructive to the ecosystem (Alawiye, 2011). The protests therefore cast some doubt on the efficacy of some of the NLNG's CRS programmes in the area. Most business organizations make concerted effort to meet the interests of stakeholders generally including host communities.

In the process of satisfying these diverse stakeholders' interests, some organization like the NLNG often finds themselves at crossroads while making CSR decisions. This situation arises because while stockholders are interested in profit maximization, other stakeholders like the community, including residents of Bonny, are always craving for more welfare packages and community development projects. This is particularly so because the operations of the NLNG have negative impact on the environment and the sources of the livelihood of residents of the host community. Therefore, to the extent that CSR has developed to become an ethical obligation by which business organisations are expected to address the social and environmental impact on the host community, it becomes pertinent to ascertain the perception of residents of Bonny regarding the NLNG CSR programmes in the area.

This becomes more compelling; in view of the NLNG sponsored programme Ibani Hour on Wazobia 94.1 FM. How effective are the CSR programmes of the NLNG towards meeting the expectations of the residents of Bonny in terms of social welfare and the amelioration of the negative social, economic and environmental impact of the company operations there? 'Therefore, this study seeks an investigation of the perception of Bonny residents of the NLNG Corporate Social Responsibility programmes from the prism of the Ibani Hour on Wazobia 94.1FM.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the perception of residents of Bonny about the Corporate Social Responsibility programmes of the NLNG Company as portrayed by Ibani Hour on Wazobia FM, Port Harcourt. Specifically the objectives are to:

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1. examine the level of exposure of Bonny residents to the Ibani Hour Programme aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM.
2. examine the extent to which Ibani Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM has influenced the perception of the CSR programmes of the NLNG among residents of Bonny.
3. Ascertain factors in the Ibani Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM that informed the perception of NLNG's CSR programmes among residents of Bonny

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the level of exposure of Bonny residents to the 'Ibani' Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM on Mondays and Thursdays?
2. To what extent has the 'Ibani' hour influenced the perception of the CSR Programmes on the NLNG among Bonny residents?
3. What factors in the 'Ibani' Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM informed the perception of the NLNG corporate social responsibility programmes among residents of Bonny?

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Evolution of Corporate Social Responsibility

The debate about Corporate Social Responsibility has been said to have begun in the early 20th century, and growing concerns about large corporations and their power. According to Sethi (2011) the ideas of charity and stewardship helped to shape the early thinking about CSR in the United States. Ida Tarbell's 1904 work, *The History of the Standard Oil Company* helped the decision of the Supreme Court of the United States to break up the company on antitrust grounds. Similarly, Upton Sinclair's 1906 book, *The Jungle*, led to the passage of the pure Food and Drugs Act and the Meat Inspection Act by the United States Congress. These as noted by Sethi (2011) can be seen as early attempts to mandate socially responsible corporate behaviour.

The term corporate social responsibility itself according to Gawel (2016) came into common use in the early 1970s although it was seldom abbreviated. The term stakeholder, meaning those impacted by an organisation's activities, was used to describe corporate owners beyond shareholders from around 1989. Many large companies now issue a corporate social responsibility report along with their annual report. The CSR report concentrates on their non-financial social activities (usually positive contributions in nature). The increased awareness of CSR had also come about according to Korten (2015) as a result of the United Nations Millennium Development Goals, in which a major goal is the increased contribution of assistance from Large Organisations, especially Multi-National Corporations, MNCs, to help alleviate poverty and hunger, and for business to be more aware of their impact on society. There is a lot of potential for Corporate Social Responsibility to help with development in poor Countries, especially Community-based initiatives. In the United Kingdom (UK), as noted by Kitten (2015) the term Corporate Responsibility is increasingly used instead of Corporate Social Responsibility, as a conscious move to expand the boundaries away from purely social or Community issues to include broader areas of governance and environmental sustainability.

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The main proponent of the need for organizations to be socially responsible to their stakeholders, Freeman (1984) described CSR as a management concept which helps organizations to incorporate both social and environmental concerns in their business operations and relationships with stakeholders. According to Brusseu (2011), corporate social responsibility could be defined in two main perspectives. Corporate social responsibility is perceived as a general name or any theory of the corporation which emphasizes both the responsibility to make money and the responsibility to act ethically with the surrounding environment and the community. On the other hand, CSR could be perceived as a specific concept to achieve profit for a corporation while it plays a role in the community welfare (Brusseu, 2011). On the whole, Brusseu (2011) summed up CSR as consisting of the following: The economic responsibility of the corporation to make money; the legal responsibility of the corporation to adhere to the rules and regulations of the community, and the ethical responsibility of the corporation to do what is right even when not required by the spirit or letter of the law.

Corporate Social Responsibility and the Environment

Initially, CSR activities do not include environmental activities even though there was recognition of the need for firms to limit their resource use and its effect on the environment (Krumwiede et al., 2012). Environmental aspects of CSR were probably first introduced by Backman in 1975 and have recently constituted an essential aspect of CSR, they include activities such as waste recycling, pollution prevention and control, green initiatives, and the efficient use of energy and resources (Krumwiede et al., 2012). Coelho et al., (2011) express the view that support for the environment is an essential aspect of the business strategy and should not be voluntary. Acceptance of such, they stated is the accomplishment of CSR in acknowledging environmental activities and their sustainability effects. It is therefore imperative, they advised, that firms meticulously evaluate each stage of their decision-making process and the effects of their decisions on their host communities and the environment. Ali and O'Faircheallaing, (2017) reveal that the activities of the oil and gas industry often commence and expose a series of environmental issues and the oil and gas industry occupy a vital place in CSR debate and how it could be actualized. It also discovered that many oil and gas firms as a regular practice incorporated environmental reporting as an aspect of their CSR activities to show their proactivity in encouraging sustainable development (Guenther et al., 2017). It is the view of Hilson and Basu, (2013) that CSR stresses the protection of the environment, a mind-set that has resulted in the extensive acceptance of the need for viable and progressive environmental management strategies. Conventionally, they stated, that approaches to CSR must include, as the least precondition, the assessment of environmental performance using appropriate indicators. Beard et al. (2011) agree that the protection of the environment should be uppermost in priority and higher in moral plinth than profit-making. It is their view that the environment is impacted in different ways by activities of firms which disrupts ecosystem, depletion of natural resources and emission of waste and pollutants. Lo, et al., (2010) suggest that the oil and gas industry is likely to be in the forefront in implementing environmental protection activities as they are more likely to be persuaded to do so by their stakeholders considering the nature of their business.

Perception

It is common knowledge that humans are creatures that are capable of processing information obtained around them. Humans can assess what they see, feel, or think. Therefore, humans can perceive something according to their thoughts. Perception is an opinion on something in an environment. Perception is a term that is closely

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related to human psychology and it has been defined in various ways. According to Martono (2015), perception is a process in assessing or building impression towards various things that exist in the human senses. Perception is a process used to analyse information provided by others. Zulhernanda (2017) states that perception is the processes whereby people select, organise, and interpret sensory stimulations into meaningful information about their work environment.

Discussion on perception often contains various meanings, the varying meanings lie in the connotation of the term perception itself. Perception according to Nurohman (2018), is the perception is defined in accordance with the opinions and views of someone. And Solso (2008) posits that perception is an advanced cognitive level in the interpretation of sensory information.

The term perception according to Lindgren (2013), perception is viewed as the mediating processes that are initiated by sensations. Clifford (2011) states that perception is the process of discriminating among stimuli and of interpreting their meanings while, Huffman and Vernoy (2010), perception is the process of selecting, organizing, and interpreting sensory data into useable mental representation of the world.

Public Enlightenment

Enlightenment has been defined as an advanced stage of getting the populace informed on their rights and duties. It also implies, keeping the general public wary of current developments that affects their living or an act of giving someone knowledge or understanding about a concept (Baje, 2018). For example, the age of Public enlightenment in Europe started during the 17th and 18th Centuries and was considered by scholars as an intellectual movement driven by reason (Baje 2018). It was an ideological and philosophical movement marked by the rejection of all conservative factors that have impeded development for a long period of time. Public education in some developed countries has kept the citizenry abreast of all issues of national importance and has played strategic role in influencing official policies and government decisions (Smith, 2009). WHO recommends 5% for Caesarean Sections. In Lagos, State government recently announced the launch of a new health insurance scheme that will make Caesarean Sections free (WHO, 2017). The concept of public enlightenment has a global relevance in all ramifications. Ayo (2018) describes public enlightenment which he also calls the ‘Age of Enlightenment,’ as a programme carried out by the government agency or an organization aimed at achieving clarity of perception, reason and knowledge in a community.

Theoretical Framework

Corporate Social Responsibility Theory

Corporate Social Responsibility Theory was propounded by Bowen (1953). Bowen, who is thought to be the “Father of Corporate Social Responsibility”, in his book, ‘Social Responsibility of the Businesses’, advocated that businesses should be carried out with ethical consideration and responsiveness to the stakeholders of society. Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR, theory, therefore, affirms that corporations are entities with economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic obligations, which implication is that corporations which stress the triple-bottom-line must endeavour to work towards sustainability of their economic, legal, social and environmental concerns. Corporate social responsibility, according to Bowen (1953) has two meanings. In the first place, CSR is the general name for any theory of the corporation that emphasizes both the responsibility to make money and the responsibility to have interaction with the surrounding community in an ethical manner. Secondly, CSR, is the

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specific conception of the responsibility of a corporation to make profit while playing a broader role in issues of community welfare (Bowen, 1953). According to Safarzard (2017), CSR is a legal requirement for a company which includes continued commitment toward the community, and which main goal is to increase the efficiency and productivity of the operations of the company and maximize its shareholders profits. However, all these must be done by integrating the ethical and environmental expectations of the community into the company's economic process.

This theory is of great relevance to this study because CSR of business organization has evolved over time to become mandatory requirements that organizations must fulfil in order to achieve their main objective of profit making in a friendly environment and community. The theory is highly relevant to the study as it provides a structured framework to evaluate the scope and impact of these initiatives. By employing CSR theory, the study can systematically analyse how NLNG's efforts align with broader social, environmental, and economic responsibilities, beyond mere profit-making. This theory aids in assessing the authenticity and effectiveness of NLNG's programmes in contributing to community development, environmental sustainability, and overall societal wellbeing in Bonny, Rivers State also, CSR theory helps in identifying potential gaps and areas for improvement in NLNG's approach, ensuring that the company's initiatives are genuinely beneficial and responsive to the needs of the local community.

Perception Theory

The proponents of this theory are Berelson and Steiner (1964). It simply states that individuals have ways of shutting out information that is not in line with what they believe in. Weimann (2010) describes perception as the "complex processes by which people select, organize, and interpret sensory stimulation into meaningful and coherent picture of the world" (p.21). It simply means that individuals most often process campaign message to suit the worldview they are conversant with. According to him, studies in human perception has shown that people's values, needs, beliefs and perceptions play important roles in determining how they select stimuli from the enormous campaign content in their environment and how they ascribe meaning to such stimuli from their existing frame of reference. Anaeto et al., (2011) posit that "the theory tells us the process of interpreting message is complex and that these goals may be difficult to achieve" (p.66).

This theory is crucial to the study as it delves into how individuals interpret and form pinions about corporate initiatives. This theory focuses on the cognitive and psychological processes that influence residents' attitudes, including factors such as communication effectiveness, cultural values, personal experiences, and media representations. By applying this theory, the study can uncover the underlying reasons behind residents' views on NLNG's CSR activities, providing insights into how these programmes are received and understood within the community. Also, analysing the role of media, such as Ibani Hour on Wazobia FM, in shaping public perception highlights the impact of information dissemination and public discourse. Understanding these perceptions is essential for assessing the actual effectiveness of CSR initiatives, ensuring they are not only well-intentioned but also positively received and impactful from the community's perspective.

2.3 Empirical Review

Eke et al. (2024) carried out a study on "Broadcast media Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDS campaign on health consciousness of Bonny residents in Rivers State." The objectives of the study were among others to examine

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the level of exposure of Bonny residents to broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs; ascertain the disposition of Bonny residents towards broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AID. Agenda setting and perception theories underpinned the study. The study employed descriptive survey design and the population of the study is 302,000. The sample size for the study was 383 using Meyer's sample table. The multistage sampling techniques were used and questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The data for this study were analysed using simple percentages and were arranged in frequency tables.

The findings revealed that the Bonny residents were occasionally exposed to broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs. Apart from the broadcast media campaign, they got information on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs through billboard, magazine and newspaper. The result revealed that they fully understood the broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs. Also, the study found out that the attitude of Bonny residents to broadcast media campaigns was that the broadcast campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs were participatory and supportive but not indifference. The study concluded that it is quite obvious the broadcast media campaigns played a significant role in making people of Bonny conscious of their health. The study recommended that broadcast stations should through their day to day reportage focus surveillance on the many ills in the society so as to use them as themes for messages. The present study and the reviewed study are both related as they centre on broadcast media and Bonny residents perception, but differ in the areas of objectives, scope and methodology. Sani and Ibrahim (2020) conducted a study on "Public perception of radio Nigeria programme 'Radio Link' in awareness creation on national issues." The study sought to find out how the audience perceives Radio Nigeria programme 'Radio Link' as a tool for creating awareness on national issues. Survey methodology was adopted for the study. Also, the study was anchored on Development media theory. A questionnaire containing multiple-choice was administered to one hundred (100) respondents randomly selected from Kaduna North local government area of Kaduna state. Data obtained from the copies of the returned questionnaires were analyzed using simple tables and percentages. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents believe that Radio Link on Radio Nigeria create awareness on national issues and provide avenue for government to get feedback on government policies. The study recommended that management of Radio Nigeria should provide enough finance to enable the programme producers perform optimally. Also, regular maintenance and procurement of equipment should be done so that breakdown in transmission will be minimized. The reviewed study and the present study are related as both studies centre on radio and developmental programme but they differ in objectives, scope and methodology.

Enobakhare et al. (2013) did a survey work on "Assessment of public awareness and knowledge of media campaigns on environmental issues in South-South zone." The study examined public awareness and knowledge of media campaigns on environmental issues in southsouth states Nigeria. It argued that media campaigns are strong instrument in public awareness on environmental issues. However the remarkable progress made by media in providing environmental information in Nigeria, there are still substantial constraints to the effective management and development of the environment. The mismanagement of environment in South-South geopolitical zones has literally contributed to the problem of erosion and deforestation which has led to deterioration of the environs. The study was anchored on two media theories- attitude change theory and social

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responsibility theory. Data were carefully collected through the instrumentality of questionnaire and were analyzed using tables, bar and pie charts.

The findings revealed that South-south populaces were aware of sensitization campaigns about environmental management issues. It also revealed that they have a good knowledge and that their attitude in regards to environmental management has changed positively as a result of the media campaigns. Based on the findings, useful recommendations were made such as the media should not down play the issue of environmental hazards. They should play the agenda function by emphasizing on the effects of environmental degradation. The reviewed study and the current study are related as both studies hinge on media campaign, resident awareness and knowledge and environmental issues but differ in the areas of objectives, scope and methods.

Onwuemene (2022) carried out a survey on “Residents’ perception on the role of mass media play in promoting gender equality in Oshimili South LGA of Delta State.” The study assessed the perception of residents on the role of mass media play in promoting gender equality in Oshimili South LGA of Delta State. Three research questions and three hypotheses were adopted for the study. The study adopted a survey research design. The target population of the study was 206,600 estimated residents from the three major towns of Oshimili South LGA of Delta State. Taro Yamene’s formula was used to derive 399 respondents that served as sample of the study. However, 256 (64.16%) out of 399 copies of the questionnaires were filled correctly. Data were collected from respondents using structured questionnaire and analysed using frequencies, percentages and mean. T-test statistic was used to test the hypotheses.

The result revealed that residents percept that media do not provide adequate attention female candidates for election, relegate women to supporting roles in politics and leadership, media report less of female politicians to maintain societal tradition. Even women who compete for and then win the top job are vulnerable to the media’s personalizing proclivities. Mass media in the area of study promoted human rights of women. Media promoted gender equality in awareness of socio-economic relevance among women folks. However, it was noted that TV and radio did not initiate series on educational initiative that raises awareness about violence against women. The study recommended among others that government through the Gender Ministry should develop a deliberate policy aimed at making media institutions more gender sensitive in their programming especially in politics and human right. The reviewed study and the current study are related as both studies focus on residents perception and the role of mass media, but the area of divergence is on the objectives, scope and methods.

Methodology

A research design adopted in this study was descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design could be likened to a building plan which guides the builder in constructing the structure. The design was used to discover people’s opinion, attitude, preference and knowledge levels about an issue like the NLNG CRS programmes in Bonny as projected on Wazobia 94.1FM during Ibani Hour, using the instrument of open-ended and close-ended self-administered questions. The population or the universe of the study comprises the total number of subjects in a research. The three communities Bonny, Akiama and Finima were purposively selected because of the noticeable impact of the business of the NLNG in the three areas. The population of the study according to the Federal Republic of Nigeria Official Gazette, the National Population Commission (2006) was 214,983. This population was projected at 2.8% growth rate for 18 years, which gave a projection of 254,820. Since the entire

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254,820 residents of Bonny, otherwise described as the entire population, could not be examined, 384 residents drawn from the population following Meyer’s (1979) sampling table was used. To get to the respondents, the researcher utilised the multi-stage sampling technique which started with the clustering of Bonny Island into three communities. Being a survey, data for this study was generated by the use of the questionnaire. The data were presented using tables and percentages and analysed with Likert Scale Mean Value using the Weighted Means Score (WMS).

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Research Questions

Table 1: Awareness of NLNG’s Ibani Hour programme Aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM

Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	379	100%
No	0	0%
Total	379	100%

From Table 1, all the respondents (379) representing 100% were aware NLNG’s “Ibani” Hour programme aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM.

Table 2: Level of NLNG’s “Ibani” Hour Programme on Wazobia FM

Options	No of Respondents	Percentage
Always	156	42%
Weekly	98	26%
Bi-weekly	75	19%
Monthly	30	8%
Rarely	20	5%
Total	379	100%

As indicated in the Table above, majority of the respondents agreed to have been always exposed to NLNG’s “Ibani” Hour programme on Wzobia FM on Mondays and Thursdays at 5 pm. This was followed by respondents on weekly, Bi-weekly, monthly and rarely respectfully.

Table 3: Awareness of Indications for Corporate Social Responsibility Programmes of NLNG on “Ibani” Hour Programme on Wazobia FM

Options	No of Respondents	Percentage
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Vocational training for youth	128	34%
Building of internal roads in Bonny	15	4%
Advocacy for residents to enrol the national health insurance scheme	102	27%
Advocacy for clean environment through proper waste disposal method	90	24%
All of the above	10	3%
None of the above	34	8%
Total	379	100%

From the Table, out of the total number of respondents sampled, majority of the respondents agreed that they were aware of the indications for Corporate Social Responsibility programmes of NLNG on Wazobia 94.1 FM. 100% of them are aware of the NLNG CRS programmes through various means. Such means are vocational training for youth, advocacy for clean environment through proper waste disposal method, advocacy for residents to enrol into the national health insurance scheme.

Table 4: Extent Ibani Hour on Wozabia 94.1 FM influenced Perception of NLNG’s CSR Programmes among Residents in Bonny

Items	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	Total	Total	Decision
Weighted (fx)							
“Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1 FM has enlightened your understanding of many significant NLNG’s CSR programme which you knew existed	102	408	134	131	162	12	984 2.60 High Extent
“Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1 FM has improved the impression you initially had about NLNG’s CSR programmes among residents of Bonny	154	616	151	74	453	0	1217 3.21 High Extent

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The positive claims on NLNG 140 CSR programme portrayed on “Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1 FM has been consistent with reality	165	71	3	1210	3.19	High Extent	
The implementation process and selection criteria for beneficiaries of NLNG’s CSR programmes highlighted on “Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1FM has been transparent and all-inclusive among residents of Bonny	151	92	157	0	1194	3.15	High Extent
The NLNG’s CSR programmes as highlighted during “Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1FM has contributed significantly to social and economic infrastructural development among residents of Bonny	169	63	153	0	1171	3.09	High Extent
The NLNG’s CSR programmes as highlighted on “Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1FM has promoted skills acquisition and empowerment among residents of Bonny	65	150	158	6	1086	2.87	High Extent
The NLNG’s CSR programmes as highlighted on “Ibani” Hour on Wazobia 94.1FM has contributed to environmental health and safety among residents of Bonny	137	152	40	50	1134	2.99	High Extent
Do you feel satisfied with the general outcome of NLNG’s CSR programmes on Ibani Hour among residents of Bonny	100	75	154	56	989	2.61	High Extent

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Weighted Mean

1123

2.96

High Extent

Data in Table 4 show that the respondents accepted that extent Ibani Hour on Wozabia 94.1 FM influenced perception of NLNG’s CSR programmes among residents in Bonny was high.

Table 5: Factors in “Ibani” Hour Programme on Wazobia FM that informed the perception of NLNG Corporate Social Responsibility Programmes of NLNG on

Options	No of Respondents	Percentage
Revival of Ibani dialect	128	34%
Enlightenment on clean environment	34	8%
Sensitisation of youth empowerment	102	27%
Accessibility of healthcare	90	24%
All of the above	15	4%
None of the above	10	3%
Total	385	100%

From the Table, out of the total number of respondents sampled, majority of the respondents agreed that the factors in the Ibani Hour programme on Wazobia 94.1FM that informed the perception of the NLNG’s CSR programmes among residents of Bonny were revival of Ibani dialect, sensitisation of youth empowerment, and accessibility of healthcare.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1: What is the level of exposure of Bonny residents to the ‘Ibani’ Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM on Mondays and Thursdays?

The result showed that all the respondents (379) representing 100% were aware of NLNG’s “Ibani” Hour programme aired on Wazobia 94.1 FM. The majority of the respondents agreed to have been always exposed to NLNG’s “Ibani” Hour programme on Wzobia FM on Mondays and Thursdays at 5 pm. They were aware of the indications for Corporate Social Responsibility programmes of NLNG on Wazobia 94.1 FM. All the respondents representing 100% of them are aware of the NLNG CRS programmes through various means. Such means are vocational training for youth, advocacy for clean environment through proper waste disposal method, advocacy for residents to enrol into the national health insurance scheme. The interview report revealed that the programme is dedicated to promoting and preserving the Ibani language, which is a significant aspect of the Bonny people’s heritage. It provided an opportunity for listeners, especially younger generations, to learn and practice the language. The programme often delves into the customs, traditions, and history of the Ibani people.

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This aspect of the show is informative for those interested in understanding the cultural dynamics of the Bonny Kingdom.

These findings are in consonant with the study of Eke et al. (2024) which revealed that the Bonny residents were occasionally exposed to broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs. Apart from the broadcast media campaign, they got information on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs through billboard, magazine and newspaper. They fully understood the broadcast media campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs. Also, the study found out that the attitude of Bonny residents to broadcast media campaigns was that the broadcast campaigns on Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDs were participatory and supportive but were indifference. The study of Sani and Ibrahim (2020) is relevant to this finding as it posited that majority of the respondents believe that Radio Link on Radio Nigeria create awareness on national issues and provide avenue for government to get feedback on government policies. The perception theory upon which this study was anchored gives backing to this finding. The theory posits that individuals tend to expose themselves to information that aligns with their interests, values and needs. The high level of awareness among Bonny residents indicates that they perceive the “Ibani Hour” programme as relevant and beneficial to them, leading to consistent exposure. This suggests that the programme effectively addresses the residents’ interests or concerns, particularly regarding NLNG’s Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives. The theory explains how the Bonny residents’ high awareness of the Ibani Hour programme is not just a result of passive exposure but is actively shaped by their selective processes of exposure, perception, and retention. These processes ensure that the programme’s content resonates with the audience, thereby increasing their awareness and understanding of NLNG’s CSR activities.

Research Question 2: To what extent has the ‘Ibani’ Hour influenced the perception of the CSR Programmes on the NLNG among Bonny residents?

From the results of the study, it was revealed that extent Ibani Hour on Wozabia 94.1 FM influenced perception of NLNG’s CSR programmes among residents in Bonny was high. Result from the interview extract revealed that the programme is tailored to the local audience and it played a crucial role in shaping public perception. The programme acted as a bridge between the NLNG and the community by providing information and addressing concerns related to CSR initiatives. The programme served as an educational platform where NLNG’s CSR activities are discussed, helping to inform the public about the company’s efforts in areas like education, healthcare, and infrastructure in Bonny.

Enobakhare et al. (2013) study is in line with this finding as their finding revealed that South-south populaces were aware of sensitization campaigns about environmental management issues. It also revealed that they have a good knowledge and that their attitude in regards to environmental management has changed positively as a result of the media campaigns. Also, Onwuemene (2022) upholds the finding of this study, as it revealed that residents percept that media do not provide adequate attention female candidates for election, relegate women to supporting roles in politics and leadership, media report less of female politicians to maintain societal tradition. Even women who compete for and then win the top job are vulnerable to the media’s personalizing proclivities. Mass media in the area of study promoted human rights of women. Media promoted gender equality in awareness of socio-economic relevance among women folks.

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The perception theory is highly relevant to the finding as it explains how individuals interpret and give meaning to information based on their cultural background, experiences, and expectations. In this context, the programme's success can be attributed to its tailoring to the local audience, which means it effectively resonates with the residents' values, language and social realities. By presenting NLNG's CSR initiatives in a way that aligns with the community's perspective, the programme shapes public perception positively, ensuring that the residents not only receive the information but also view it through a favourable lens.

Research Question 4: What factors in the 'Ibani' Hour Programme on Wazobia 94.1 FM informed the perception of the NLNG corporate social responsibility programmes among residents of Bonny?

The results revealed that the majority of the respondents agreed that the factors in the Ibani Hour programme on Wazobia 94.1FM that informed the perception of the NLNG's CSR programmes among residents of Bonny were revival of Ibani dialect, sensitisation of youth empowerment, and accessibility of healthcare. The interview report equally showed that the programme, which is sponsored by NLNG and produced by Grafton entertainment, focused on promoting and preserving the Ibani language, culture, and history. It provides a platform that not only educates the local population about their language but also highlights the contributions of NLNG to the Bonny Kingdom. The findings support the study of by Enobakhare et al. (2013), which revealed that South-south populaces were aware of sensitization campaigns about environmental management issues. They have a good knowledge and that their attitude in regards to environmental management has changed positively as a result of the media campaigns.

The social responsibility theory hold sway here, it states that business have an obligation to act in ways that benefit society at large. The Ibani Hour programme's focus on culturally and socially significant issues, such as the revival of the Ibani dialect, youth empowerment, and healthcare accessibility, reflects NLNG's dedication to fulfilling its social responsibility. By addressing these critical areas, NLNG not only contributes to the wellbeing of the Bonny community but also deeply with the residents, thereby enhancing its reputation as a society responsible entity.

Conclusion

The study established the programme's effectiveness as a communication and engagement tool. The high level of awareness among the residents indicates that the programme is achieving its goal of informing the community about NLNG's contributions and efforts to support local development. This reflects positively on NLNG's commitment to transparency and community involvement, strengthening its relationship with the residents of Bonny

The high influence of the "Ibani Hour programme on the perception of NLNG's CSR initiatives among Bonny residents underscores the programme's effectiveness in communicating and promoting these initiatives. The programmes' success is largely due to its strategic alignment with the local audience's culture and needs, which has played a crucial role in shaping a positive public perception of NLNG. This study highlights the importance of culturally tailored communication in influencing public opinion and building trust within the community.

The study concludes that the emphasis on the revival of the "Ibani dialect, youth empowerment, and healthcare accessibility underscore the effectiveness of the focus areas in shaping public perception. The alignment of the programme's content with the community's cultural and social needs has significantly contributed to the

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favourable view of NLNG among residents. This highlights the importance of addressing local priorities in CSR communications to foster trust and engagement within the community.

This study provides valuable insights into how media, specifically, radio programmes like “Ibani Hour” on Wazobia 94.1 FM, shape public perception of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives. It highlights the role of localised media in influencing community opinions about large corporations like NLNG, which can inform both media strategies and corporate communication efforts. The research contributed to the broader understanding of how residents in resource-rich areas like Bonny perceive CSR initiatives. It underscores the importance of tailored communication strategies that resonate guiding other companies operating in similar contexts to enhance their CSR engagement and effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. NLNG should leverage this platform “Ibani Hour” to further communicate its on-going and future CSR initiatives as consistent engagement and transparent communication will help maintain and potentially increase the positive perception of NLNG’s CSR efforts among the residents of Bonny
2. NLNG should invest further localising the content, ensuring that it continues to reflect the community’s interests, language, and values. Therefore, NLNG could explore opportunities to expand the programme’s reach by incorporating digital platforms or community events that engage residents directly.
3. NLNG should consider developing complementary initiatives or partnerships that deepen its impact on youth empowerment, healthcare, and cultural preservation. By maintaining a strong focus on the issues that matter most to the Bonny community. NLNG can reinforce its commitment to social responsibility and strengthen its relationship with local stakeholders.

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